

World-travellers from Bengal in the Late Nineteenth and Early Twentieth Century

Ankana Bag (M.Phil)

Ph.D. Scholar, Centre for Comparative Literature, Bhasha Bhavana, Visva-Bharati

Abstract: For a long time, travel writing has been a means of learning about new and distant things through the act of travelling or moving physically from one location to another. The type of "knowing" that forms the basis of travel writing often contains notes of power imbalance because a traveler in a "postcolonial" world is either viewing another space (through their travels) from a position of power or from the position of a disempowered individual in the scale of colonial relations. One of the main reasons why travel literature, both as a genre and as individual works, examines these tensions and interactions is because of the way the traveler's sight is shaped by their location. Bengal in nineteenth-century India saw a sharp rise in the number of travelers and the first-person accounts of these journeys after the social stigma against traveling overseas gradually subsided with the establishment of a colonial education system for the upper classes. Some Bengali travelers broadened their horizons and included the 'world' in their itinerary. Globetrotting, or traveling across many different nations, or what is sometimes referred to as the 'world,' was a very European concept. In other words, writing about traveling through the world meant presenting readers with the viewpoint of the traveler. In order to examine how Bengali world-travelers perceived and presented distinct worlds to their intended audience—which varied depending on the purpose of their journeys—this article focuses on the writings of Pratap Chandra Mozoomdar, Krishnalal Basak, Ramnath Biswas, Bimal Mukherjee, and Sharatchandra Basak.

Keywords: Bengal, travel writing, globetrotter, Ramnath Biswas, colonialism

For a long time, travel writing has been a means of learning about new and distant things through the act of travelling or moving physically from one location to another. Since a traveler in a 'postcolonial' world is either viewing another space (through their travels) from a position of power or from the position of a disempowered individual in the scale of colonial relations, the kind of 'knowing' that forms the core of travel writing frequently carries notes of power imbalance. Mary Louis Pratt explains this imbalance in *The Imperial Eye* (1992) in terms of contact zones produced by colonialism, which are places where cultures clash and engage, frequently in the context of wildly disparate power dynamics.

Travel writing as a genre and as individual texts are sites of examining such conflicts and encounters for a variety of reasons; the traveler's gaze being influenced by their locatedness being a major one among them. After the societal prejudice against travelling abroad progressively faded with the introduction of a colonial education system for the higher classes, Bengal in nineteenth-century 'India' experienced a significant increase in the number of travellers and the documentation of these journeys in first-person accounts. Some of the notable names of the contemporary travelers at that time include Krishnabhabini Debi, Trailokyanath Mukhopadhyay, and Shibnath Shastri. Some travellers from Bengal expanded their travels in a wider scale and added the 'world' to their itinerary. Globetrotting, the practice of touring through numerous countries, or what is commonly summed up as the 'world,' was a distinctly European idea. To put it another way, writing about travelling through the 'world' involved giving readers the traveler's perspective on the world. In addition to discussing the traveler's point of view, it also provided an insight into how the traveler was forming their own identity in light of the world they experienced. The 'world' that the Bengali travellers explored in the latter part of the nineteenth and early twentieth century was rife with conflicts over colonialism, the emergence of

nationalism and capitalism in various forms, advancements in certain fields of technology, and literary systems negotiating new genres. This article focusses on the writings of Pratap Chandra Mozoomdar, Krishnalal Basak, Ramnath Biswas, Bimal Mukherjee, and Sharatchandra Basak in order to explore how Bengali world-travelers saw and portrayed separate worlds to their intended audience that differed based on the objectives of their travels.

The writing of Pratap Chandra Mozoomdar is the oldest of the five names enumerated above. A prominent member of the Brahmo Samaj, P. C. Mozoomdar, or Pratap Chandra Mozoomdar, travelled to multiple countries around the world to give lectures propagating Brahmoism. In 1858, he joined the Brahmo Samaj under Keshub Chunder Sen's leadership, and he was a distant relative of the latter. The book, *The Oriental Christ* (1883) by P. C. Mozoomdar was the catalyst for his rise to prominence and helped him enter a dialogue with the esteemed Indologist Max Muller. Additionally, he represented the Brahmos (school of thought) at the renowned Parliament of World Religions in 1893. Among the places he visited were England, the United States, Germany, Japan, China, and Singapore. S.K. Lahiri's publishing house published his book, *Sketches of a Tour Round the World*, in 1884. His travels and his life as a devout Brahmo are covered in sections of the book. Among the notable people he met were Ralph Waldo Emerson and Harriet Beecher Stowe, two well-known American authors. One of the first, if not the first, personal account of Japan penned by a Bengali can also be found in this text. According to the author, the Hindu traveler is viewed as an oddity among other Indian and foreign tourists, and this was something that he personally experienced during his travels far and wide.

His observations of the American people significantly include a description of the African-American population, particularly the African-American men he refers to as 'the

emancipated Negro.’ He notes their appearance, temperament, food-habit, as well as their position at work as waiters or coachmen. However, he sensed that strife and discontent between the ‘White’ American populace and the African-American people were always simmering just under the surface of the society and he also learned that people of mixed parentage were looked down upon by the ‘White’ Americans. When Ramnath Biswas, another and perhaps the most famous Bengali world-traveller visited America approximately fifty years after the time that P. C Mozoomdar was describing, he also noticed the aggressive racism in America and wrote elaborately upon it. P. C Mozoomdar states that he noticed while the African-American men can serve as waiters or coachmen, they themselves did not have the right to enter the first class hotel or travel by the Pullman palace car, or admit their children in the “great colleges” (Mozoomdar 57) of the country. He states with conviction that even though he had addressed large audiences in America several times, he cannot remember seeing even a single African-American face among those who came to hear him talk about Brahmoism.

Bichitra Bhraman (1921) by Krishnalal Basak can be considered as another addition to the literary texts that featured some form of globetrotting. Krishnalal Basak was different from all the other Bengali travellers because his travels were due to his work in different circus troupes. He was a professional gymnast and acrobat who performed all over the world. He was born in Bengal in 1866 and developed a strong interest in gymnastics at an early age. At the age of eighteen, he joined a group called Indian Circus, which was led by a European known as Harrington. He left home and travelled to many places throughout his career as a circus artist. His itinerary spanned from Burma, Singapore, Java, Srilanka, Hongkong, China, Russia, Japan, Philipines, France and even to Australia which was quite a rare destination for Bengali travellers at that time. Krishnalal Basak’s account of Australia is perhaps one of the earliest first-hand

accounts about Australia composed by any Bengali. He recounts going to visit the 'Chamber of Horrors' in Melbourne, which refers to the Waxwork Exhibition commenced by Madame Sohier back in 1857 and at the time of Krishnalal Basak's visit was owned by Maximilian Kreitmayer. It housed touring attractions, wax-figures of the royal family, of notable politicians and celebrities, but also effigies of Australian murderers and robbers (often portrayed as engaged in an act of violence). He writes that he found these displays disturbing even though he thought that perhaps the vivid morbidity of these exhibits played some indirect role in decreasing criminal activities locally. He moved from one troupe to another pretty frequently, with occasional returns to his home in Kolkata. In 1900, after he had returned to Kolkata after performing in various locations in Australia with the Harmston Circus, he was recruited to perform at the Paris Exposition of 1900 along with artists from other parts of India. At that time he was able to experience staying in Paris for months, visiting the Hippodrome theatre, Eiffel tower, Casino de Paris and Tour de Monde.

The last chapter of his travel account details how he established his own circus titled the Great Eastern Circus in Kolkata in 1901 and continued to tour with his own troupe for years, performing both at home and abroad. The chapter also provides a meticulous list of places and dates where the circus had performed from 1901 to 1914. He talks about memorable moments between these fourteen years in the rest of the chapter. It's interesting to note that, in contrast to the earlier chapters, which included his perspective as a member of the troupes, this chapter, which mostly describes the period when he owned a troupe, does not discuss the culture and people of the many nations he had visited. Instead, the fact that the anecdotes in this chapter focus on the reception of his circus, their struggles, and their victories may be due to the shift and

increase in his personal responsibility that came with holding a position of power (the owner) in the circus troupe.

Bimal Mukherjee embarked on his bicycle 'world tour' in 1926, which continued until 1937. But only later, in a single anthology called *Duchakay Dunia* (1986), was Bimal Mukherjee's narrative of his travels published. His itinerary included stops in East Asia (China, Thailand, and Japan), West Asia (Iraq and Saudi Arabia), and Europe (England, Italy, and Germany). Having started out with very little money, he had to work at a variety of professions to continue earning the money he needed to travel. He held jobs as a pilot, sailor, photographer, and helper on fishing trawlers and dairy farms. He also gave lectures on his experiences and travels and had temporary teaching jobs at children's schools. He had conducted most of his travels by a bicycle, much like Ramnath Biswas who set out on a world-tour a few years after Bimal Mukherjee. His journey, which the author presents as akin to a pilgrimage in which he was impacted by everyone he met and helped him expand his horizons, is primarily focused on his interactions with people and the challenges of the journey. He also came to believe that his presence and travels have influenced others in turn. One such instance occurs when, while touring in Italy, he is asked to give lectures at Padua University. His first lecture at the meeting of the Institute of Cultures was about Rabindranath [Tagore] and Santiniketan, after which he is asked to give a second lecture on 'Gandhiji and Freedom'. He was able to feel that his lectures had moved his audience and made them sympathetic towards the cause of the freedom movement in India.

Ramnath Biswas started the first phase of his world tour on a bicycle in 1931 from Singapore. Many of the countries that he travelled to were either directly under colonial rule or were colonisers or existed in a middle space trying to come to terms with its colonial experience.

He wrote a large number of travel narratives based on his memories and journal and published them throughout the 1940s and well into the 1950s as well. His observation of Korea and China under the direct colonisation of Japan in early 1930s can be mentioned as an instance. He critiques capitalism in the guise of imperialism in both the countries and states in *Dwichakre Korea Bhraman* (1949) and *Lal Chin* (1941) that he believes both countries can thwart colonisation by fueling the 'emergent' inclination towards ideas disseminated through Communism among the 'common' people. He saw a South Africa that was heading towards apartheid in *Ondhokarer Africa*. He observed the racial hierarchy in which the European colonists and the Indian traders from Gujarat both double-discriminated against the original inhabitants of South Africa. Additionally, he observed how the cultures of countries like Thailand and Burma reacted to the cross-cultural Hindu 'influence.' For instance, he observed how the stories ascribed to the *Ramayana* became a component of Siamese folk performances and documented this in his book *Sarba Swadhin Shyam* (1949). He was among the first Bengali travellers to visit Africa extensively and write about his experiences in a number of travelogues. South Eastern Africa had a rise in nationalist sentiment in the 1930s. According to Walter Rodney's 1981 book *How Europe Underdeveloped Africa*, educated elites and the expanding middle classes started to oppose colonial dominance and push for more political participation and autonomy. While activists and intellectuals were crucial in igniting nationalist movements, during his travels, Ramnath Biswas himself observes that such movements and sensibilities were not limited to intellectuals or the well-educated. Even the farmers and labourers in East Africa long for independence, Ramnath asserted in his books, referring to groups such as the National Congress of Tanganyika (NCT) (in modern-day Tanzania) and the African National Congress (ANC) in South Africa which were forums for expressing anti-colonial feelings and calls for

self-determination. Through political activism and mobilisation, these movements aimed to bring disparate ethnic communities together and challenge colonial rulers.

Dr. Sharatchandra Basak is another name who is referred to as a ‘globetrotter’ in the Prabasi periodical. In the ‘Reviews’ section of the thirty eighth volume of Prabasi (1938), Shailendrakrishna Laha reviews the book *Bhu-parjyatan* (Touring across the World) by Dr. Sharatchandra Basak. The reviewer writes that the well-printed book contains a lot of pictures as well. The book describes the travels undertaken by the author in England, France, Germany, Turkey, Russia, Poland, China, Japan, the United States of America and the islands of Hawaii. The reviewer observes that at that point of time the Bengali literary market was saturated with travel accounts about England, France and Germany as many people from Bengal used to travel to Europe, and followed a specific itinerary through these countries. But first hand travel narratives about countries like Turkey and Russia from a Bengali point of view were far and few in between. He asserts that discussions based on firsthand knowledge of the recently established statecraft in Russia and Turkey were much more engaging to read than descriptions of picturesque locations. It seems that Dr. Sharatchandra Basak shared this opinion and came to Russia via Poland to observe the changes the Bolshevik regime had brought about in people's lives and occupations. It should be noted that ever after the establishment of the Bolshevik government Russia had drawn the interest of the entire world into its national workings and Bengal was not an exception in this either. The thinkers and activists who were actively engaged in the nation-building project and the Swadesi movement in Bengal were looking towards different country's governing systems and models of nationalism in search of ideas and ways. Therefore, these narratives of travelling across the world also perhaps served that function of trying to build the identity of Bengal and its people in respect to the rest of the world. The

reviewer also comments that Sharatchandra Basak had tried to assess Russia's progress from a neutral standpoint and commends this effort. He has also quoted the author directly from the preface of the book where he had written about himself "I can understand it well that there is a peripatetic concealed in me. Therefore, I could not be content with touring Europe even after five times. I again had to prepare myself and set out". This shows that the Bengali globetrotters visiting many countries that were not usually visited by the other travellers from Bengal was a significant aspect of their popularity. There are a few scattered mentions of 'globe-trotters' in different Bengali texts of that time. For example, the twenty sixth volume of *Bharatabarsa* (1938) periodical published an article titled "China Dasyuder Haate" ('In the hands of Chinese dacoits') by Khsitishchandra Bandyopadhyay who is bestowed with the epithet Bhuparjyatak or world-traveller even from the content list.

All the 'globetrotters' discussed in this paper had their own agendas of travelling. Whether it was for preachings of Brahmoism, performing as a part of a circus troupe, travelling to understand the people of the world better, travelling just for the sake of it, or travelling for adventures and thrill, the different approaches to travel not only shaped each individual's worldview, but also their travel narratives. This is the very reason why in many cases the same geographical places have been experienced and expressed differently by the travelers, because each of them were rooted in their own spatio-temporal consciousness, cultural baggage of their own cultures and their subjectivity. In other words, 'globetrotting' did not remain just physical journeys for them but transformed into mental journeys as well.

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